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2 **Title:** Fine Scale Determinants of Soil Litter Fauna on a Mediterranean Mixed Oak
3 Forest Invaded by the Exotic Soil-Borne Pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*

4 Alejandro Jiménez-Chacón¹, Pablo Homet², Luis Matías^{2,3}, Lorena Gómez-Aparicio^{2*},
5 Oscar Godoy^{2*}

6 ¹ Master's Degree Program, Advanced Biology Research and Application. Edificio
7 Verde, Universidad de Sevilla, Calle Profesor García González, s/n, 41012 Sevilla,
8 Spain.

9 ² Instituto de Recursos Naturales y Agrobiología de Sevilla, Consejo Superior de
10 Investigaciones Científicas (IRNAS-CSIC), Avenida Reina Mercedes, 10, Sevilla,
11 41012, Spain.

12 ³ Departamento de Biología Animal, Biología Vegetal y Ecología, Facultad de Ciencias
13 Experimentales, Universidad de Jaén. Campus Las Lagunillas SN. 23009, Jaén, Spain.

14 * Corresponding authors: ogodoy@irnas.csic.es, lorenag@irnase.csic.es

15 telf: +34 954 62 4711

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24 **Abstract**

25 There is growing recognition of the importance of soil fauna for modulating nutrient
26 cycling processes such as litter decomposition. However, little is known about the
27 drivers promoting changes in soil fauna abundance on a local scale. We explored this
28 gap of knowledge in a mixed oak forest of Southern Spain, which is under decline due
29 to the invasion of the exotic soil-borne pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. Meso-
30 invertebrate abundance found in soil litter was estimated at the suborder level. We then
31 explored their statistical correlations with respect to light availability, tree and litter
32 characteristics, and *P. cinnamomi* abundance. Oribatida and Entomobryomorpha were
33 the most abundant groups of Acari and Collembola, respectively. According to their
34 trophic level, predator and detritivore abundances were positively correlated while
35 detritivores were, in turn, positively correlated with pathogen abundance and negatively
36 influenced by light availability and tree defoliation. These overall trends differed
37 between groups. Among detritivores, Diplopoda preferred highly decomposed litter
38 while Oribatida and Psocoptera preferred darker environments and Poduromorpha were
39 selected for environments with lower tree defoliation. Our results show the predominant
40 role of light availability in influencing litter fauna abundances at local scales and
41 suggest that the invasive soil-borne pathogen *P. cinnamomi* is integrated in these
42 complex relationships.

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44 **Keywords:** detritivores; forest decline; invasive species; invertebrates; light
45 availability; litter depth; mesofauna; soil humidity; soil-borne pathogens; *Quercus*
46 *canarensis*; *Quercus suber*

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49 1. Introduction

50 There is growing recognition that soil fauna plays a major role in litter
51 decomposition [1,2]. The way soil fauna mediates litter decomposition involves several
52 simultaneous processes. As soon as leaf litter falls from trees, invertebrate detritivores
53 start feeding and breaking litter down into small pieces. This fragmentation process
54 increases the litter surface area by accelerating the inoculation and activity of bacteria
55 and fungi that transform these smaller pieces into inorganic molecules such as
56 phosphate, water, carbon dioxide, or ammonium [3–5]. Parallel to this herbivory
57 process, soil litter contains different groups of predators by controlling the abundance of
58 these invertebrate detritivores through a diverse range of feeding strategies [6]. These
59 multi-trophic interactions result in complex processes that are responsible for creating
60 soil fertility, maintaining soil health [7], and determining carbon budgets [8]. Despite
61 the importance of soil fauna providing ecosystem services and economic profit [9-11]
62 through their role in nutrient cycling, the drivers of soil fauna distribution and
63 abundances at regional and local scales are still poorly understood [7]. Obtaining such
64 knowledge is a critical first step in evaluating the contribution of soil fauna to forest
65 functions and for taking informed decisions in land forest management while preserving
66 its biodiversity [12].

67 Mediterranean forests are relatively rich in soil litter fauna groups and the
68 determinants of their abundances have been studied on a local scale. A recent
69 experiment manipulating the amount of rainfall according to future climate change
70 scenarios has found that rainfall reduction influences the distribution and abundance of
71 litter detritivores. Additionally, these invertebrates are less abundant in dry microsites
72 [13]. Yet forests are inherently complex ecosystems and a wide variety of factors
73 besides precipitation can, in principle, generate different microhabitats by supporting
74 different species and food webs. As previous knowledge of these relationships was
75 relatively scarce, the first steps of research in this regard selected as many variables as
76 possible. For instance, Reference [12] considered 125 potential drivers of soil

77 invertebrate diversity at local scales within temperate forests in Poland. However, the
78 possibility to evaluate such a high number of predictors is often limited in many cases,
79 which calls for an alternative approach to come up with specific hypotheses in order to
80 narrow the number of predictors down. Therefore, we devote the rest of the introduction
81 to explain our main predictions of the abiotic and biotic determinants of soil litter
82 invertebrate abundances within a Mediterranean mixed oak forest in Southern Spain,
83 which is under decline due to the invasion of the exotic soil-borne pathogen
84 *Phytophthora cinnamomi* [14] (see Figure 1).

85 Given that Mediterranean forests have a limited amount of rain throughout most
86 of the year and that litter humidity strongly influences invertebrate diversity [12,13], it
87 seems reasonable to start disentangling this complexity by studying those abiotic drivers
88 leading to fine-scale variation in soil litter moisture. Light availability, which is
89 heterogeneous in space and time in Mediterranean forests [15], can strongly reduce litter
90 moisture [16]. It has also been shown that litter moisture suffers less fluctuations with
91 litter depth and deeper layers retain higher levels of moisture for longer [17]. Several
92 biotic drivers can simultaneously influence or be correlated with the depth of the litter
93 layer. Tree size and their associated litter pools are the two most clearly biotic
94 determinants of litter depth. Bigger trees are expected to create greater litter pools
95 within the tree neighborhood and create deeper litter layers. Finally, mixed litter coming
96 from different tree species at different decomposition stages increases the availability of
97 different soil litter fauna niches [18].

98 Most forests within the Mediterranean basin are far from pristine due to their
99 history of human use. In particular, they are affected by the unintentional introduction
100 of exotic pests and pathogens, which can fundamentally change the forest composition
101 and structure [19,20]. Exotic soil-borne pathogens, for example, are behind some of the
102 most aggressive plant diseases on earth, which cause severe damages in plant tissues
103 and eventually lead to the death of whole individuals [14,21–23]. Such negative effects
104 directly influence the biotic determinants of soil litter fauna through changes in the litter
105 fall amount and chemistry and indirectly influence the biotic determinants of soil litter

106 fauna by modifying physical factors such as temperature, soil moisture, and light
107 interception [24–27]. Which drivers are more strongly modified by soil-borne pathogens
108 and by the particular effect of *P. cinnamomi* depends on the stage of the tree disease. At
109 earlier stages, tree defoliation increases litter fall and soil litter pools. As a result of this
110 initial defoliation, litter layers tend to be deeper and soils receive higher pulses of
111 organic matter, but, as the disease progresses, defoliated trees contribute less to the litter
112 pools and lead to an increase in light availability. This in turn can raise soil temperature
113 and reduce litter humidity.

114 The main aim of our study is to understand the abiotic and biotic determinants of
115 fine scale distribution and the abundances of soil fauna associated with forest litter
116 within a forest decline context. To reach this goal, we conducted an observational study
117 in the Alcornocales Natural Park (Southern Spain). This park contains the largest and
118 best conserved forests of cork oak (*Quercus suber*) in Europe. However, since the early
119 1990s, a severe decline affecting the *Quercus* species has been reported in the park and
120 throughout the Mediterranean Basin largely due to the exotic soil-borne pathogen
121 *Phytophthora cinnamomi* Rands. [28–31]. The introduction and spread of this pathogen
122 from its native range in the New Guinea-Celebes region is presumed to be due to human
123 activity and now it is considered a major ecological and economic problem [32–34].
124 The *P. cinnamomi* disease causes a series of symptoms ranging from progressive
125 defoliation and loss of vigor to death [35]. Its dispersal is strongly determined by soil
126 water availability [36]. Moreover, prior work within an area close to this study has
127 shown that the pathogen has the potential to attain high densities at local scales [14].

128 We specifically conducted a structural equation modeling approach to determine
129 which abiotic and biotic drivers determine the observed variation in the abundance of
130 soil fauna invertebrates found in forest litter and the differences between major trophic
131 groups (detritivores versus predators [11]). The final model selected goodness of fit
132 requirements that departed from our theoretical expectations of the direct and indirect

133 paths by which abiotic and biotic forest drivers modify litter meso-fauna abundances
134 (see Figure 1). Complementarily, we also conducted multivariate analyses to explore the
135 mayor axes of local environmental variation separating differences in abundances
136 within the major groups of detritivores and predators.

137

138 **2. Material and Methods**

139 2.1. Study Site

140 The study was conducted in the Alcornocales Natural Park (see Figure 1A), which is a
141 hotspot of biodiversity in Southern Spain [37]. The climate is sub humid Mediterranean.
142 The annual mean temperature is 16.3° C and annual mean precipitation is 748 mm (50-
143 year average, IFAPA). 95% of precipitation occurs from October to May. Soils are
144 sandy, acidic, and nutrient poor. The soils are also derived from bedrock dominated by
145 Oligo-Miocene sandstones. The area of our study is a mixed forest where *Q. suber*
146 coexists with the deciduous shade-tolerant *Q. canariensis*. A closed canopy
147 characterizes this forest with little understory shrub vegetation composed of isolated
148 individuals of *Erica* ssp.

149

150 2.2. Experimental Set Up

151 This observational study was conducted within the frame of a recently built long-term
152 research infrastructure and was aimed at evaluating the combined effect of climate
153 change and the exotic soil-borne pathogen *P. cinnamomi* on forest dynamics and
154 functioning. In more detail, we established 6 plots of 20 m × 15 m at Gamir (Cádiz,
155 Spain, 36°34'07.5''N 5°32'08.3''W) during early spring 2016 (see Figure 2A). These
156 plots were specifically built to reduce the amount of rainfall by 30%. This percentage
157 corresponds to the average reduction of rainfall according to a restrictive future climate
158 change scenario for Southern Spain (model CMIP5 for the scenario RCP 8.5 for the
159 period 2081-2100 in comparison with the period 1986-2005, [38]). Three of these plots

160 had a structure of rain exclusion while the other three were assigned to control (see
161 Figure 2B). The rainfall exclusion treatment was formed by a metal structure supporting
162 plastic PVC gutters that covered 30% of the plot area in order to exclude a similar
163 amount of natural precipitation [39]. On the control plots, identical gutters were placed
164 upside down to make the albedo and the understory microclimate was as similar as
165 possible in both treatments following previous experiences with this type of rainfall
166 exclusion infrastructure [39]. For both types of plots, we also considered an edge effect
167 of 1 meter in which no measurements were taken of the tree standing at the edge [39].
168 Finally, all plots were selected to have similar conditions in terms of slope, aspect, and
169 number of trees. We decided to perform our experiment within this research
170 infrastructure for two main reasons. First, the rainfall structure treatment has the
171 potential to create differences in litter humidity between treatment plots and control
172 plots. Second, we have readily available information of spatial variation at local scales
173 of several abiotic and biotic variables that could influence litter mesofauna abundances,
174 which was explained in the introduction (see Figure 1).

175

176 2.3. Collection of Soil Fauna Invertebrates and Characterization of Litter Properties

177 We collected litter samples from the forest floor in early March 2017 in order to
178 capture the largest amount of litter at the end of the leaf shedding process in *Q.*
179 *canariensis*. Litter samples were collected directly from the ground and underneath the
180 canopy of individual trees in order to relate mesofauna abundances to the micro-
181 environmental conditions associated to each tree. We selected 3-4 trees of *Q.*
182 *canariensis* per plot with a total of 22 trees. Some of these trees had no symptoms of *P.*
183 *cinnamomi* infection while others showed minor to moderate leaf defoliation. We
184 defined the forest litter as any type of organic material coming directly from tree
185 individuals that are not decomposed and show partial signs of decomposition. This
186 definition includes both leaf and wood material. Following this definition, we collected
187 all organic material under the canopy of each tree within an area of 20 cm × 20 cm from

188 the top of the litter layer down to the top of the mineral soil layer. At the time of
189 collection, we estimated litter depth as the average value of three measurements using a
190 ruler. Litter samples were stored in hermetic plastic bags and put in a cooler with ice for
191 transporting to the lab in order to minimize water and mesofauna losses.

192 Immediately after litter samples were brought to the lab, we weighed the litter
193 sample and then we used the Tullgren funnel method [40] over the next ten days to
194 obtain mesofauna associated with fresh litter. We dried an aliquot of the initial fresh
195 litter sample at 40°C over three days. Then this dried aliquot was weighed to estimate
196 the percentage of water in the sample. With the dry litter, we estimated the proportion of
197 the total sample in terms of weight belonging to different tree species and to different
198 decomposition stages. For the classification according to different tree species, we
199 distinguished between three categories including litter coming from *Q. suber*, *Q.*
200 *canariensis*, and other tree species. For the classification according to the litter
201 decomposition stage, we separated each litter sample into three different categories.
202 Level 1 involved low decomposition in which litter leaves were undamaged or
203 unbroken. Level 2 included medium decomposition in which litter leaves were broken
204 in smaller pieces and level 3 consisted of high decomposition in which litter leaves were
205 broken in very small pieces and it was impossible to distinguish parts of litter leaves in
206 the sample.

207 Arthropods were stored in 70% ethanol and separated in different groups with a
208 binocular scope. We focused on several groups of mesofauna found in the litter
209 samples. Specifically, these groups were Acari (separated in three different suborders
210 (Oribatida, Mesostigmata, and Prostigmata), Collembola (separated in four different
211 morphological groups (Sympleona, Entomobryomorpha, Poduromorpha and
212 Neelipleona), Araneae, Pseudoscorpionida, Isopoda, Thysanoptera, Myriapoda,
213 Lepidoptero, Psocoptera, and Diptera. In the last step of the analysis, we assigned each
214 group a trophic role involving either detritivores or predators, according to previous
215 studies [6,18,41–43] (see Figure 3). Diptera were classified as detritivores since all
216 individuals found were larvae. Likewise Myriapoda individuals were classified as

217 detritivores since they belong to Diplopoda. Enchytraeidae individuals were not
218 included in the analyses because the method used to estimate mesofauna abundance
219 (i.e., a dry extraction) does not serve well for an accurate estimation of individual
220 abundances of this particular group. Finally, our expertise did not allow us to estimate
221 Astigmata abundances separate from Oribatida abundances. Astigmata mature
222 individuals are very similar in their morphology to immature individuals of Oribatida.
223 They have been classified together in the recent past. We acknowledge that this is a
224 limitation of our study when addressing the determinants of different group of
225 detritivores. However, we believe this is a minor limitation since Astigmata tends to be
226 much less frequent than Oribatida [44]. In addition, both groups are detritivores, which
227 means that this misclassification does not alter the total estimates of detritivore versus
228 predator abundances in our samples.

229

230 2.4. Characterization of Fine-Scale Variation in Abiotic and Biotic Determinants of Soil 231 Fauna under Field Conditions

232 At the time of litter collection, we measured several abiotic and biotic micro-
233 environmental conditions in the field in order to explore the determinants of the soil
234 litter fauna composition and abundance at local scales (see Table 1). Soil humidity in
235 the top 10 cm of the soil was measured with a PR2 Profile Probe, Delta-T Devices
236 (UK). Light availability was measured by hemispherical photography [45]. Photographs
237 were taken at ground level using a horizontally levelled digital camera (Nikon, Tokyo,
238 Japan) and aimed at the zenith by using a fish-eye lens of a 180° field of view (FCE8,
239 Nikon). The images were analyzed using the Hemiview software (1999, delta-T
240 Devices, Cambridge, UK) to calculate the global site factor (GSF), which integrates the
241 total amount of light over the whole year and ranges from 0 (light absence) to 1 (100%
242 light availability).

243 Regarding the biotic microenvironment, we measured the size and degree of
244 defoliation of the canopy tree right above each of the litter samples collected as well as
245 the amount of *P. cinnamomi* in its soil. Tree size was quantified using the standard
246 Diameter at Breast Height (DBH) method using a measuring tape. Defoliation was
247 visually characterized using a semi-quantitative scale ranging from 0 (no defoliation) to
248 3 (high defoliation). The abundance of the soil-borne pathogen *P. cinnamomi* was
249 measured in soil aliquots of 10 g as described in Reference [31]. Briefly, we prepared
250 soil suspensions in 100 ml of water–agar 0.2 %. Afterward, aliquots of 1 ml taken from
251 the soil suspensions were plated onto NARPH Petri dishes (20 dishes per sample).
252 Colonies growing on the plates were morphologically identified and counted. Since soil
253 samples had been dried previously, it was assumed that each colony resulted from the
254 germination of at least one resistant spore (oospore or chlamydospore). Results were
255 expressed as colony-forming units per gram of dry soil (cfu g⁻¹). Finally, we measured
256 soil respiration with an IRGA (Infrared gas analyser, Li-COR 6400x) on 10 cm pipe
257 sections installed in the field [46].

258

259 2.5. Data Analysis

260 We first performed pairwise correlation to make sure that the environmental
261 predictors selected were not highly correlated (Pearson-r > 0.8) (Appendix, Table 1).
262 Then we transformed several environmental variables for further analysis following
263 standard procedures [13]. Specifically, we transformed light availability using arcsine
264 square root transformation and log-transformed the soil density of *P. cinnamomi*, the
265 invertebrate's abundances, and litter mass. In addition, the matrix containing
266 abundances for the different groups identified across all sites was squared-root
267 transformed and then standardized using a Wisconsin double standardization following
268 Reference [13].

269 To understand the direct and indirect effects of litter properties and
270 environmental predictors on the abundance of the forest litter mesofauna, we conducted

271 structural equation modeling (SEM) techniques by using the “lavaan” package [47].
272 From the initial path diagram built according to our a priori expectations (see Figure 1),
273 we finally selected one that had an optimal fit according to several statistical indices
274 recommended [48]. The set of indices selected to test the goodness of statistical fit were
275 the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), the comparative fit index (CFI),
276 and the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR). According to previous
277 research [48,49], the criteria for selecting the best-fit model was the following: RMSEA
278 < 0.05 , CFI > 0.90 , and SRMR < 0.10 . If two models successfully accomplished these
279 criteria, we selected the one that minimized towards zero RMSEA and SRMR values
280 but maximized towards CFI values.

281 For the second set of statistical analyses, we were looking to explore the abiotic
282 and biotic determinants of the composition of the detritivore and predatory mesofauna
283 found in our litter samples. Accordingly, we performed Non-metric multidimensional
284 scaling (NMDS) analyses using package “vegan” [50], which contain a version of
285 Clarke and Ainsworth BIOENV analysis [51] that compares distance/similarity matrices
286 with environmental variables for potentially explaining differences in soil litter fauna
287 composition. For conducting NMDS analysis, we first calculated distances between
288 groups using the Bray-Curtis distance index, which ranges between 0 and 1 [52].
289 Afterward, we used the function “bioenv” to determine which abiotic and biotic drivers
290 determine variation in litter mesofauna. Finally, we used the function “bvstep” to know
291 which groups of soil litter mesofauna were more responsive to the selected
292 environmental variables. We used a stress level ≤ 0.2 to account for the goodness of fit
293 in the NMDS analysis. All statistical analyses were conducted with R software (R
294 version 3.3.2, 2016-10-31).

295

296 **3. Results**

297 **3.1. Abundance of Litter Mesofauna**

298 We collected a total of 9324 arthropods in our litter samples. The most abundant
299 group was Acari, which represented the 81.81% of the total number of individuals
300 collected while Collembola represented only the 14.63%. Among mites, Oribatida
301 (detritivores) was the most common group followed by Mesostigmata and Prostigmata
302 (predators). Entomobryomorpha was the most frequent group within Collembola
303 (86.52%) followed by Symphypleona (6.59%), Poduromorpha (6.23%), and
304 Neelipleona (0.65%) (see Figure 3).

305

306 3.2. Direct and Indirect Determinants of the Abundance of Detritivore and Predatory 307 Mesofauna

308 The path diagram selected to explain the abundance of detritivore and predatory
309 mesofauna in forest litter showed that the presence of both groups was strongly
310 correlated (0.77), which supports the idea that predators are intimately linked to prey
311 abundances (see Figure 4). The main environmental variable directly influencing
312 detritivore and predator abundance was light through a negative effect (−0.50 and −0.40,
313 respectively). *P. cinnamomi* density was positively correlated with detritivore
314 abundances (0.51) and to a lesser extent with predators (0.24). Tree size negatively
315 influenced detritivores abundance (−0.28), and tree size was weakly correlated with
316 light availability (−0.03) (see Figure 4).

317 Surprisingly, litter moisture was not selected for the final path diagram with the
318 best fit. This result is probably due to the fact that the rainfall enclosure did not create
319 enough variation across samples. We only found a marginally significant difference in
320 litter moisture between control and treatment plots (litter moisture values 37.1 ± 3.0 and
321 35.9 ± 2.3 for control and treatment plots, respectively, and ANCOVA using litter depth
322 as a covariable, $F = 2.97$ and $P = 0.076$).

323

324 3.3. Multidimensional Analyses Relating to Environmental Predictors to Mesofauna 325 Composition

326 The results of the NMDS analyses showed that including light availability, tree
327 defoliation, high decomposed litter, and soil respiration explained the highest amount of
328 variation for detritivore mesofauna across samples (rho index= 0.27). These
329 environmental predictors accounted mostly for variation in the abundance of Diplopoda,
330 Pscoptera, Oribatida, Diptera, and Poduromorpha (rho index=0.86). Specifically,
331 Diplopoda was positively associated with highly decomposed litter and Psocoptera and
332 Oribatida were positively associated with higher levels of tree defoliation. In contrast,
333 Poduromorpha avoided places with high tree defoliation and light availability. Larvae of
334 Diptera were positively associated with the amount of soil respiration (see Figure 5).

335 NMDS analysis also showed that the best set of environmental predictors
336 explaining the variation in predator mesofauna were wood mass and litter mass and
337 depth (rho index = 0.30). This is a similar value of explained variance compared with
338 that obtained for detritivores, which suggests that we captured the variation in
339 detritivores and predators abundances although the specific determinants were different
340 (see Figure 5 and Figure 6). Among the four different predator groups, wood, and litter
341 characteristics significantly captured variation for all groups except Araneae (rho index
342 = 0.94). In particular, Mesostigmata individuals tended to prefer areas with a greater
343 amount of wood and litter while Prostigmata and Pseudoscorpionida tended to prefer
344 areas with deeper litter layers (see Figure 6).

345

346 **4. Discussion**

347 Understanding basic forest ecosystem processes such as litter decomposition and
348 nutrient cycling would strongly benefit from characterizing the abundance and
349 composition of mesofauna associated with forest litter. This is an especially urgent need
350 for Mediterranean forests since many of these forests are currently being affected by
351 several global change drivers such as climate change and the invasion of exotic species
352 [14,53,54].

353 In our study, the estimated abundance of the different groups of soil litter
354 mesofauna is comparable to what has been observed in other forests with similar (e.g.,
355 France [18]) and different climatic conditions (e.g., Wales [55] and Sweden [56]). In all
356 these forest systems, there was a much higher abundance of detritivore Acari and
357 Collembola than of predators. Acari Oribatida was by far the main detritivore group and
358 Acari Mesostigmata was the most frequent group of predators (see Figure 3). Both
359 Acari and Collembola have been extensively studied as environmental indicators of soil
360 quality [57,58] and our analyses clearly selected light availability as the most important
361 predictor of their abundances (see Figure 4). This result agrees with previous studies
362 pointing out to light availability as a main determinant of soil fauna [12] although the
363 sign of the light effect varied among studies. In our system, detritivores preferred darker
364 microsites (see Figure 4) while in previous studies conducted in cool temperate forests,
365 light had a positive effect on mesofauna abundance [12]. These discrepancies between
366 studies could be related to differences in the identity of the main limiting factors of
367 mesofauna abundance and activity. In cool temperate forests, low temperatures could
368 strongly limit mesofauna activity, which would benefit from the higher temperatures of
369 lighter microsites [12,59,60]. However, in water-limited Mediterranean forests,
370 mesofauna benefit from the higher moisture found in darker microsites [61]. Given
371 these differences, future work should address how the signs and strength of the local
372 determinants of soil fauna abundances change across continental gradients.

373 The complexity of the litter structure is often a good predictor of the abundance
374 and diversity of soil litter fauna. Soils with more litter biomass and even mixtures of
375 litter from different tree species are expected to have a higher diversity and abundance
376 of different soil fauna groups because they allow for higher numbers of microhabitats
377 and therefore increase niche differentiation between groups [17,18,62]. In our study,
378 litter characteristics play a less important role compared to light availability. None of
379 them were included in the structural equation model (see Figure 4) yet they had a
380 significant association with the abundances of particular groups of detritivores and
381 predators (see Figure 5 and Figure 6). For instance, Diplopoda and Psocoptera, two

382 detritivore groups, were positively associated with the decomposition state of the litter
383 whereas Mesostigmata and Prostigmata, two groups of predators, were positively
384 associated with the amount of litter mass and depth, respectively. This highlights that
385 soil litter mesofauna cannot be seen as a group of generalist fauna and different taxa
386 within and between trophic groups clearly selected for different microenvironments.

387

388 It is still poorly understood how soil-borne pathogens causing forest decline
389 affect the abundance and distribution of invertebrate mesofauna associated with forest
390 litter. Therefore, we were particularly interested in understanding these relationships
391 given the unique experimental location of our experiment. Because the abundance of *P.*
392 *cinnamomi* in the soil of Mediterranean forests show a predictable spatial structure
393 associated to highly defoliated oak trees [14], we expected that the loss of tree vigour
394 and biomass caused by *P. cinnamomi* infection would modify soil mesofauna
395 communities indirectly through changes in the local abiotic and biotic environments.
396 Specifically, our expectations were that, at early stages of pathogen infection, these
397 indirect effects might occur because tree defoliation increases the litter depth while, at
398 the final stages, the lack of tree crown would increase light availability in the forest
399 understory and reduce soil and litter moisture. In our study, the path model selected did
400 not support the notion that these indirect effects are important for determining soil litter
401 fauna abundances. In fact, such a model did not support our original hypothesis that *P.*
402 *cinnamomi* indirectly influences mesofauna abundances by increasing light availability
403 due to tree defoliation (see Figure 1). It was included as an indirect path connecting *P.*
404 *cinnamomi* abundances with litter depth. Instead we found an unexpected correlation
405 between *P. cinnamomi* with detritivores and predator abundances. With the information
406 collected in this study, the main mechanisms behind this association cannot be isolated,
407 but can be proposed. Direct feeding effects of detritivores on *P. cinnamomi* are unlikely
408 unless it occurs accidentally due to enormous differences in size. However, they could
409 potentially disperse its chlamyospores. A more plausible explanation would be that

410 both groups would share niche characteristics by inhabiting soils under defoliated trees
411 enriched in organic matter from dead roots and leaves. For instance, prior work has
412 independently shown that both detritivores and *P. cinnamomi* are selected for higher
413 organic matter and soil nutrient availability [63,64].

414 Regarding the effect of tree size on mesofauna abundances, the structural
415 equation analysis showed a negative effect of this biotic variable on detritivore
416 abundances but not on predator abundances. To our knowledge, there is only one other
417 study evaluating the role of tree size on soil invertebrate groups. Specifically, Reference
418 [12] found that the tree basal area, which is a variable related to tree size, had a positive
419 effect on the abundance of some groups (e.g., Collembola) but negative effects on ants.
420 Why tree size produces these opposing effects on the abundance of different groups of
421 invertebrates was unclear in that study. The same situation happens in our case. We
422 originally hypothesized that bigger trees are taller and this correlation would translate
423 into lower light availability (see Figure 1), but our model did not support this possibility
424 (tree size and light availability were weakly correlated, Figure 4). Another potential
425 explanation could be that soil fauna prefers moderate levels of litter humidity.
426 Therefore, bigger trees would accumulate more litter by maintaining high levels of
427 humid litter that are not selected by detritivores. Unfortunately, our results did not
428 support such a relationship either.

429 Our study is limited by its relatively low sample size. The 22 litter samples taken
430 are a consequence of the strong effort we put in characterizing the local condition as
431 exhaustively as possible. This sample size seems to capture relatively well one third (~
432 30 %) of the variance in abundances across locations of the different groups of
433 detritivores and predators (see Figure 5 and Figure 6). However, two thirds of variance
434 were not properly explained by our NMDS models. Additionally, sampling more trees
435 at different times and more local environmental variables such as soil fertility and
436 abundances and composition of soil fungi is desired [65]. This procedure could serve to
437 better understand the mechanisms behind the unexpected negative direct relationship
438 between tree size and the overall abundance of detritivores and predators or perhaps

439 provide novel explanatory paths (see Figure 4). It also might help to clearly distinguish
440 the role of litter moisture in determining soil litter fauna abundances. In this regard, we
441 had little variation in the percentage of litter humidity between control and rainfall-
442 exclusion plots.

443 Overall, we have found that light availability is the main determinant of soil
444 fauna negatively influencing the most common groups of detritivores (Acari and
445 Collembola) found in the litter of mixed oak forest in Southern Spain. This effect is
446 likely due to its negative effect on soil and litter humidity. Nevertheless, different litter
447 characteristics such as litter mass, depth and degree of decomposition, and—to a lesser
448 extent—other local biotic variables such as tree defoliation and soil respiration were the
449 main predictors of the abundance of specific groups of detritivores and predators. The
450 abundance of the invasive soil-borne pathogen *P. cinnamomi* was not related to any
451 indirect path determining the abundance of soil litter mesofauna through their effects on
452 tree defoliation. However, it was directly and positively correlated with both the
453 abundance of detritivores and predators. These results suggest that this invasive
454 pathogen species is integrated in these multitrophic interactions occurring between soil
455 litter mesofauna guilds.

456

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647 **Table 1.** Abiotic and biotic drivers included in this study to assess variation in soil

648 litter fauna abundance and composition. Units are specified.

	Variable	Units	Mean \pm Standard error
Abiotic	Light availability	Glare Spread Function values (GSF)	0.336 \pm 0.016
	Soil humidity	% volumetric water content	20.618 \pm 1.022
	Wood	Grams (g)	13.997 \pm 1.682
	Litter depth	Centimeters (cm)	4.268 \pm 0.235
	Litter moisture	% water in mass	36.586 \pm 1.956
Biotic	Soil respiration	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	5.685 \pm 0.358
	Tree size	Diameter at breast height (dbh) in cm	37.455 \pm 3.624
	Tree defoliation	From 0 (no defoliation) to 3 (full defoliation)	0.636 \pm 0.151
	Litter <i>Q. canariensis</i>	Grams (g)	9.724 \pm 0.930
	Litter <i>Q. suber</i>	Grams (g)	7.941 \pm 0.683
	Litter other species	Grams (g)	0.088 \pm 0.086
	Litter non identifiable	Grams (g)	41.355 \pm 5.299
	Decomposition level 1	Grams (g), litter low decomposed	11.028 \pm 1.084
	Decomposition level 2	Grams (g), litter medium decomposed	6.725 \pm 0.601
	Decomposition level 3	Grams (g), litter highly decomposed	41.355 \pm 10.270
	Pathogen (<i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>)	Colony Forming Units/Grams (CFU g ⁻¹)	105.636 \pm 23.707

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651 **Figure 1.** Conceptual diagram outlining general direct and indirect effects of light
 652 availability, litter, tree, and soil properties, and the abundance of the pathogen *P.*
 653 *cinnamomi* on litter mesofauna abundances. This conceptual diagram served as a
 654 starting point to finally select the best-supported diagram by the structural equation
 655 analyses presented in Fig. 4.

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659 **Figure 2.** A) Location of “Los Alcornocales Natural Park” in South Spain. Our
660 observational study took place within a long-term research infrastructure. This
661 infrastructure aims to study the interactive effects of climate change and the invasion of
662 the exotic oomycete *P. cinnamomi* on forest dynamics. B) Photograph illustrating the
663 structure of rainfall exclusion. Note that to exclude water, shelters were placed upwards.
664 We used this infrastructure to promote differences in soil litter humidity between
665 climate control and drought induced plots.

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670 **Figure 3.** Histogram of the accumulated number of individuals (in logarithmic scale)
671 estimated across all litter samples for each soil litter fauna group. Soil litter fauna were
672 further classified into detritivores (yellow) or predators (blue).

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676 **Figure 4.** From the theoretical expectations of the relationships between
677 environmental predictors and mesofauna abundances presented in Fig.1, this is the path
678 diagram selected that meet the statistical requirements to conduct a structural equation
679 model. Lines in green correspond to a positive effect or correlation between variables
680 whereas lines in red correspond to a negative effects or correlations. Colour intensity is
681 positively related to the significant relationship between two variables. Single-head
682 arrows indicate that one variable exerts an effect on another variable, whereas double-
683 head arrow indicates mutual interference. In this SEM model, minimum function test
684 statistic was 0.144, with 3 degree of freedom, $P = 0.986$ and generally residual was
685 approximately 1. RMSEA = 0.000, CFI = 1.000, and SRMR = 0.030.

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690 **Figure 5.** Non-metric multidimensional analyses exploring which abiotic and biotic
691 drivers (left panel) explain variation in detritivores composition (red panel) across
692 samples (red numbers). One sample in these analyses was considered an outlier and
693 therefore removed because its soil humidity was twice the standard deviation of the
694 average soil humidity across samples.

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699 **Figure 6.** Non-metric multidimensional analyses exploring which abiotic and biotic
700 drivers (left panel) explain variation in predator composition (red panel) across samples
701 (red numbers). As in Fig.5, one sample was considered an outlier and therefore
702 removed.

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